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Anatomy of the Carotid Body of Buffalo

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The carotid body is a specialized structure located or buried in arterial connective tissue at the origin of occipital artery in cattle (Najafi *et al.*, 2008). It measures changes in blood pressure and the composition of arterial blood including the partial pressure of oxygen and carbon dioxide which are also sensitive to changes in blood temperature and pH (Eken *et al.*, 2008) in Angora rabbit. The structure and location of carotid body was noted in dog and cat (Chungcharoen *et al.*, 1952). But information on the above is meager in buffalo. Hence, the present study was undertaken due to its importance and lack of information in buffalo.

Materials and Methods

In the present study carotid bodies of 6 non-descript buffalo calves were used. After embalming carotid arteries, its branches were dissected carefully and gross morphological features of carotid body were recorded which included its anatomical location, blood and nerve supply. Then tissue pieces were collected at the junction of common carotid artery and origin of occipital artery and they were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin and processed by acetone benzene schedule. The paraffin sections of 5-6 μ sections were

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Fig. 1

Fig. 1: Photograph of buffalo calf showing common carotid artery (CCA), External maxillary artery (EMA), External carotid artery (ECA), Occipital artery (OA), Pharyngeal artery (PA), Glossopharyngeal nerve branch (N) and Carotid body (CB).

subjected to Harris haematoxylin and eosin-phloxine method (Singh and Sulochana 1997) for normal histomorphology.

Results and Discussion

In the present study carotid body was noted as a bulbous swelling at the origin of occipital artery. Eken *et al.*, (*loc.cit*) reported the carotid bodies between the maxillary and the caudal auricular arteries in Angora rabbits, whereas, Khamas *et al.*, (2002) observed carotid bodies of the mule at the angle between the internal and external carotid arteries.

These bodies were innervated by the large and distinct branches of the glossopharyngeal nerve. These branches were large and very distinct. In the present study, carotid bodies received blood from branches of occipital and pharyngeal arteries. Similar observations were also noted by Najafi (*loc. cit*) in buffalo and Chungcharoen *et al.* (*loc. cit*) in

Fig. 2: Photomicrograph of carotid body of buffalo calf showing Type-1 (T1) and Type-2 (T2) cells and Capsule (C).

Haematoxylin and Eosin X 400.

dogs. Addison and Comroe (1937) in dogs reported that the artery supplying carotid body lost most of its muscular coat and assumed a vein like appearance near the carotid body attachment. Contrary to this in rabbits carotid body receives blood supply from branches of the external carotid and internal carotid or carotid bifurcation (Chungcharoen, *loc. cit*).

In the buffalo carotid bodies were located in connective tissue layer of arterial wall of occipital artery. Carotid body was surrounded by connective tissue capsule composed mainly of collagen fibers. These observations are in accordance with the Khamas *et al.*, (*loc. cit*) in mule. Further, Khamas *et al.*, (*loc. cit*) in mule noted that several trabeculae penetrated the carotid body, which divided it into number of lobules. But in the present study no such lobules were found in the carotid bodies of buffalo.

The cells of the carotid body were arranged in groups and they were surrounded by connective tissue capsule called glomus as reported by Dellmann (1993) in domestic animals, Khamas *et al.*, (*loc. cit*) in mule and

Dowd (*loc. cit*) in *Tachyglossus*. In this two types of cells were observed viz., small darkly stained and large likely stained cells. Dellmann (*loc. cit*) in domestic animals and Eken *et al.*, (*loc. cit*) in mule named these cells as Type 1 and Type 2 cells respectively.

The Type 1 cells contained many granules and showed large, rounded or oval shaped nucleus. The Type 1 cells were arranged in groups or clusters, whereas, the Type 2 cells were elongated and darkly stained. They contained heterochromatin and no granules were found in these cells. The Type 1 cells were incompletely invested by the several Type 2 cells.

Summary

In buffalo carotid bodies were present in the connective tissue layer of occipital artery at its origin. It appeared like a bulbous swelling within the wall of the artery. It was supplied by branches of occipital and pharyngeal arteries. Carotid bodies were innervated by branches of glossopharyngeal nerve. Carotid

body consisted of two types of cells namely, Type 1 and Type 2 cells. These cells were surrounded by collagenous connective tissue capsule called glomus.

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